

S2 Tableau : Elemental composition of *O-ECB* and green synthesized AgNPs

Chemical element	Enantia chlorantha bark extract, dry		Solution of synthesized AgNPs	
	Mean fluorescence intensity, cps/uA	Standard deviation	Mean fluorescence intensity, cps/uA	Standard deviation
Si	0,0581	0,0024	0,0529	0,013
S	0,2052	0,0028	0,5193	0,0175
Cl	2,5942	0,0097	0,0485	0,0055
K	0,6511	0,0010	0,0460	0,0451
Ca	0,6185	0,0253	-	-
Mn	0,1482	0,0033	-	-
Fe	3,4854	0,0127	-	-
Zn	0,1624	0,0014	-	-
Br	4,6529	0,0114	-	-
Ag	-	-	0,6489	0,0236